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A comprehensive description of the circulating tumor cell: Hotair.

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The circulating tumor cell (CTC) is most likely responsible for effective metastasis (1-3). We measured total transcription in circulating tumor cells isolated from the blood of women with stage IV breast cancer to define at the molecular level the most significant changes that accompany dissemination in a migrating tumor cell population (4) and integrated these with transcriptomic study of the circulating tumor cell in humans with metastatic prostate cancer (5). We identify here Hotair as a differentially expressed target in the circulating tumor cell in humans with castration resistant metastatic prostate cancer.

1 Circulating tumor cells are likely the tumor cell population that function in dissemination and do so by
2 seeding distant organ sites. We defined the CTC transcriptome, describing the most significant changes
3 by target and using normal blood cells from the peripheral blood as a control reference transcriptome.

4 **Results**

5 **Figure 1:** Hotair is differentially expressed in the circulating tumor cell.

- 6 I. CTC from humans with stage IV breast cancer (peripheral blood).

7 *n*=1 normal white blood cells from the peripheral blood (human)

8 *n*=5 circulating tumor cells; humans with metastatic prostate cancer ; peripheral blood

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GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
100124700	3.12E-05	4.982	-4.164393	-20.746757	4.39E+02	HOTAIR	1619/26194	93.8

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11 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the CTC of humans with prostate cancer
12 relative to normal white blood cells using a second microarray dataset (6) from independent
13 investigators and a separate patient cohort, we validated differential expression of Hotair in humans with
14 metastatic solid tumor type. (**Chart 2**). The expression of Hotair here changed more than nearly 95% of
15 the human transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case,
26,194 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of Hotair
16 messenger RNA in the CTC indicating up-regulation of Hotair disease progression and metastasis from
17 primary tumor to CTC during the tumor life cycle. Hotair was not measured in the RNA-sequencing set we
18 utilized for study of the CTC in women with metastatic breast cancer.

19 Thus, differential and increased expression of Hotair is a defining change of the circulating tumor cell
20 gene expression signature in humans with metastatic prostate cancer.

21 **Discussion**

22 We provided evidence here that Hotair is a molecular target of modulation in the CTC. This
23 included a panel of cell surface markers, some of whose expression was conserved as marking the CTC
24 in prostate cancer but of some of whose expression was specific to the circulating tumor cell in humans
25 with metastatic breast cancer.
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Methods

We utilized GSE113890 (4) for this transcriptome study of the circulating tumor cell in humans with cancer, measuring whole transcription in CTC isolated from peripheral blood from humans with stage IV breast cancer, as compared to normal cells from the peripheral blood (along with a second dataset GSE202650 (5) studying the CTC in humans with prostate cancer for target validation) using RNA-sequencing and R-based computational methods (GEO2R).